

Review

A review of cybersecurity guidelines and standards for connected medical devices

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Introduction: Connected medical devices have introduced a new era in healthcare characterized by innovation and technology. These advancements enhance the care ecosystem, significantly benefiting providers and patients while introducing new risks regarding cybersecurity. To ensure product safety and effectiveness, manufacturers must align with regulatory requirements by implementing robust cybersecurity practices to protect medical devices effectively. However, there is currently no general approach to determine which cybersecurity-related standards should be integrated into the device cybersecurity lifecycle activities.

Objective: This review seeks to identify the existing standards, regulations, and guidelines applied to European medical devices and to describe gaps, inconsistencies, and redundancies within the frameworks.

Methods: This review is based on PRISMA-S. Five standard databases were searched using the defined related search terms in September 2024, including ISO, IEC, IEEE Xplore, ANSI & ETSI. Depending on each of the databases, search terms included "Medical Device," "Information security," "cybersecurity," "Medical equipment, software, & systems," "Information Technology," "wearable electronic devices & technologies," "security," "eHealth" and "Medical device security." An additional search of the EU Lex database using the "advanced search" feature, conducted on 9 October 2024, using two primary keywords, "Medical device" and "cybersecurity." A third search was conducted in the MDCG guidelines database using the term "cybersecurity."

Results: The search identified 473 standard publications, of which 30 standards met the inclusion criteria. These documents included published standards that were not withdrawn or

drafted. A search conducted on EUR-LEX produced 1,078 results, 17 legally binding documents meeting the inclusion criteria. 1 guidance document was included.

Discussion: The review highlights variability and gaps in cybersecurity standards and guidelines for connected medical devices. While foundational requirements, such as system compliance and architecture, are emphasized, critical areas like SBOM updates are underrepresented. Overlapping and inconsistent standards hinder streamlined compliance, underscoring the urgent need for harmonized, adaptable, and comprehensive frameworks. Regulatory overlaps, like GDPR and NIS Directive, further complicate compliance for medical device manufacturers.

Keywords: medical devices; cybersecurity; regulatory science; policy

1. Introduction

The integration of cybersecurity into the medical device industry is driven by the need to protect patient safety and security and maintain device functionality [1,2]. Connected medical devices, which have introduced advancements in healthcare by enabling remote/home patient monitoring and more accurate diagnoses and treatments [3–5], are susceptible to cyber threats that could endanger patient safety [6,7]. Examples include unauthorized access, data breaches, and the direct manipulation of device functions [1,8]. Ensuring robust cybersecurity measures is critical to safeguarding patient trust and maintaining device functionality [9].

National and International standards, guidelines, and regulations established by supranational organizations, interest groups, or regulatory bodies play a crucial role in addressing these concerns and safeguarding the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of medical devices [2,10]. To achieve this, manufacturers must comply with a structured framework of requirements aligned with regulatory standards [2]. This framework comprises multiple interconnected components, including technical standards, guidelines and process standards, and overarching regulatory directives, as shown in **Figure 1**, which collectively govern and standardize the development, implementation, and evaluation processes [11].

Figure 1. The regulatory framework.

The initial step toward achieving compliance with current regulations involves identifying the cybersecurity standards relevant to the products in question [12]. Within the European Union, several recognized standards, including ISO/IEC 27001, offer comprehensive guidelines for embedding security measures throughout the product life cycle [13]. These standards provide organizations with a structured approach to implementing effective cybersecurity practices while aligning with regulatory requirements [14]. Given the dynamic nature of the cybersecurity landscape, organizations must remain informed about emerging standards [2]. Regularly reviewing and adapting to updated guidelines and standards not only reinforces compliance but also improves the organization's reputation and ensures product competitiveness in a market where security is increasingly prioritized [11].

However, achieving cybersecurity compliance is challenging. Standards and requirements are not always clearly defined and may overlap, complicating their implementation [10,15,16]. Furthermore, the threat landscape is constantly evolving, with security measures effective today potentially becoming obsolete tomorrow [6]. Noncompliance can result in weak security, potentially harming patients, financial penalties, and damaging an organization's reputation [7].

This review examines current regulations, guidelines, and standards relevant to the EU jurisdiction. The objectives are to (1) analyze the scope and coverage of regulations, guidelines, and standards and (2) describe gaps, inconsistencies, and redundancies within the framework, providing a critical assessment of areas requiring further attention or improvement.

2. Methods

This systematic review is based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [17]. As the sources are standards, guidelines, and legislations, deviations from the protocol were required. Considering these sources, no quality assessment has been done.

2.1 Search strategy

Three independent searches were conducted to identify relevant guidelines, standards, and legislation relevant to the EU jurisdiction. The bibliographic data of all identified documents was gathered in an electronic database. Duplications were removed by a human reviewer comparing the bibliographic metadata of a document.

2.2 Standards

The first document search was conducted on September 2nd, 2024, and a second on September 25th, 2024, in five databases for International standardization organizations that provide the relevant standard publications in English: the International Standard Organization (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE Xplore), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). Each standard publication database was searched using standardized search terms adapted for each database. The ISO database was searched for "Medical Device" AND "Information security," "Medical Device," "cybersecurity," and "Health Informatics" AND "information security." The IEC database was searched for "Medical equipment, software, & systems," "Information Technology," and "wearable electronic devices & technologies." The CEN/CENELEC database was searched for "medical device and security in related commissions. ANSI searched for "Medical device security." IEEE Xplore searched for "cybersecurity" and "medical devices." The ETSI database was searched for "eHealth" and "cybersecurity".

Standards issued by different entities were considered only once to ensure comprehensiveness and avoid duplication. The final approved version of the standards is included.

2.3 Legislations

The primary search was conducted on October 9th, 2024, in the EU Lex database using the "advanced search" feature. This search employed two primary keywords, yielding 1,078 results. Subsequently, a secondary screening process was performed utilizing additional keywords: "cybersecurity," "security," "health," and "medical."

2.4 Guidelines

The "Guidance-MDCG endorsed documents and other guidance" database has been searched using the term 'Cybersecurity.'

2.5 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Sources were included in the review if they met the following inclusion criteria: (1) the source is a standard describing medical device cybersecurity requirements; (2) the source delivers guidance for the medical device cybersecurity standards. Sources were excluded when they (1) were not relevant for medical devices; (2) when they were limited to a specific subclass of medical devices and not generalizable (e.g., EMI); (3) when they were about medicinal products, (4) when the content of the source was insufficient to undertake a scientific analysis.

2.6 Study selection

One researcher screened the titles and summaries of the identified sources between September 2nd, 2024, and October 2nd, 2024, to evaluate whether they met the criteria for inclusion. A second reviewer verified the screening. After the initial screening, one reviewer screened the full text of the included guidelines for eligibility.

2.7 Data extraction

The data extraction and analysis were conducted using Excel and Word 2019. One researcher identified keywords related to the medical device cybersecurity requirements and to cybersecurity risks within each standard. Any standards and recommendations relating to both topics and the intersection of both were extracted.

2.8 Data synthesis and analysis

The extracted data and the relations between different data sources were then summarized using figures, tables, and narrative summaries. Requirements regarding cybersecurity considerations in the standards, legislations, and guidelines provided in the documents were listed.

3. Results

3.1 Search results

The systematic search was conducted across eight databases (ISO, IEC, IEEE Xplore, CENELEC, ANSI, ETSI, EU-LEX, and MDCG), yielding 1,546 documents. 1,423 documents were excluded based on titles and keywords after screening. The remaining 123 documents underwent full-text review, resulting in the exclusion of 75 additional documents. Ultimately, 48 documents were included in the final analysis. The detailed flowchart illustrating the screening and selection process is presented in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the screening process.

3.2 Source characteristics

Among the 48 documents included in the study, 17 are regulations, 30 are standards, and 1 is a guidance document. The legislative and guidance documents are exclusively applicable within the European Union, whereas the standards, though international in scope, are particularly relevant to and widely applied within the European medical device sector. The standards retrieved from the ETSI database were screened and excluded following a full-text review, as they predominantly address cybersecurity in the context of IoT devices rather than healthcare devices. **Table 1** provides an overview of the included documents. A detailed description of the documents is provided in the **Appendix, Table S1**.

Table 1. Characteristics of included documents. The table provides the complete name of the sources and the type of document.

	Document Title	Type
1	ISO TS 11633-1: 2019 Health informatics — Information security management for remote maintenance of medical devices and medical information systems	Standard
2	ISO TS 11633-2:2021 Health informatics — Information security management for remote maintenance of medical devices and medical information systems Part 2: Implementation of an information security management system (ISMS)	Standard
3	ISO TS 82304-2:2021 Health software Part 2: Health and wellness apps — Quality and reliability	Standard
4	ISO IEEE 11073-40101:2022 Health informatics — Device interoperability	Standard

	Part 40101: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Processes for vulnerability assessment	
5	ISO IEEE 11703-40102:2022 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 40102: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Capabilities for mitigation	Standard
6	IEC 80001-2-2:2012 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-2: Guidance for the communication of medical device security needs, risks and controls	Standard
7	IEC 80001-1:2021 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software	Standard
8	ISO TS 23535:2022 Health informatics — Requirements for customer-oriented health cloud service agreements	Standard
9	ISO IEC TS 27100:2020 Information technology — Cybersecurity — Overview and concepts	Standard
10	ISO TR 11636:2009 Health Informatics — Dynamic on-demand virtual private network for health information infrastructure	Standard
11	ISO TR 18307: 2001 Health informatics — Interoperability and compatibility in messaging and communication standards — Key characteristics	Standard
12	ISO IEC TR 22417:2017 Information technology — Internet of things (IoT) use cases	Standard
13	ISO 14971:2019 Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices	Standard
14	IEC TR 80002-1:2009 Medical device software Part 1: Guidance on the application of ISO 14971 to medical device software	Standard
15	IEC TR 80002-2: 2009 Medical device software Part 1: Guidance on the application of ISO 14971 to medical device software	Standard
16	IEC 62304: 2006 Medical device software — Software life cycle processes	Standard
17	IEC TR 80001-2-9:2017 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-9: Application guidance — Guidance for use of security assurance cases to demonstrate confidence in IEC/TR 80001-2-2 security capabilities	Standard
18	ISO TR 24971: 2020 Medical devices — Guidance on the application of ISO 14971	Standard
19	ISO TR 80001-2-6: 2014 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-6: Application guidance — Guidance for responsibility agreements	Standard
20	ISO TR 80001-2-7: 2015 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices — Application guidance Part 2-7: Guidance for healthcare delivery organizations (HDOs) on how to self-assess their conformance with IEC 80001-1	Standard
21	ISO 81001-1:2021 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security Part 1: Principles and concepts	Standard
22	ISO 27799:2016 Health informatics — Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002	Standard

23	EN IEC 81001-5-1: 2021 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security Part 5-1: Security — Activities in the product life cycle	Standard
24	ISO TR 11147:2023 Health informatics — Personalized digital health — Digital therapeutics health software systems	Standard
25	AAMI TIR57:2016 Principles for medical device security - Risk management	Standard
26	IEEE 11073-10700: 2024 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 10700: Point-of-care medical device communication — Standard for base requirements for participants in a Service-oriented Device Connectivity (SDC) system	Standard
27	IEEE 11073-10207:2017 IEEE Health informatics--Point-of-care medical device communication Part 10207: Domain Information and Service Model for Service-Oriented Point-of-Care Medical Device Communication	Standard
28	IEEE 11073-20701:2020 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 20701: Point-of-care medical device communication — Service oriented medical device exchange architecture and protocol binding	Standard
29	IEEE Std 2851:2023 IEEE Standard for Functional Safety Data Format for Interoperability within the Dependability Lifecycle	Standard
30	IEC 80001-2-3:2012 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-3: Guidance for wireless networks	Standard
31	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1078 of 14 April 2021 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2021/523 of the European Parliament and of the Council by setting out the investment guidelines for the InvestEU Fund	Regulation
32	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/30 of 29 October 2021 supplementing Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the application of the essential requirements referred to in Article 3(3), points (d), (e) and (f), of that Directive (Text with EEA relevance) *referred to as the Radio Equipment Regulation (EU) 2022/30	Regulation
33	Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 of 17 May 2019 concerning restrictive measures against cyber-attacks threatening the Union or its Member States	Regulation
34	Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU (Text with EEA relevance) *referred to as the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe.	Regulation
35	Council Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 of 19 November 2021 establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe and repealing Regulations (EC) No 219/2007, (EU) No 557/2014, (EU) No 558/2014, (EU) No 559/2014, (EU) No 560/2014, (EU) No 561/2014 and (EU) No 642/2014 *referred to as the Single Basic Act.	Regulation
36	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) (Text with EEA relevance) Text with EEA relevance *referred to as the NIS 2 Directive.	Regulation
37	Directive (EU) 2022/2557 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on the resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/E (Text with EEA relevance) (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the CER Directive.	Regulation
38	Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) (Text with EEA relevance)	Regulation

	* commonly known as the Cybersecurity Act.	
39	Regulation (EU) 2022/123 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 January 2022 on a reinforced role for the European Medicines Agency in crisis preparedness and management for medicinal products and medical devices (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the EMA Reinforced Role Regulation,	Regulation
40	Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2023 on machinery and repealing Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 73/361/EEC (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the Machinery Regulation	Regulation
41	Regulation (EU) 2023/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe's semiconductor ecosystem and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Chips Act) (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the Chips Act	Regulation
42	Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the Data Act	Regulation
43	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the Artificial Intelligence Act,	Regulation
44	the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance)) * referred to as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Regulation
45	the proposed regulation of EHDS (Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the European Health Data Space) * referred to as the European Health Data Space (EHDS)	Regulation
46	the MDR (Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance)) * referred to as the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR)	Regulation
47	the IVDR (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU (Text with EEA relevance)) * referred to as the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR)	Regulation
48	MDCG 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices	Guideline

3.3 Analysis of standards

The requirements of the 30 included standards could be categorized into two main categories: “Cybersecurity Lifecycle activities” and “Cybersecurity Technical considerations.” The first category provides foundational and process requirements for the whole product life cycle, while the second category addresses specific technical requirements and specifications. Both main categories contain 11 thematical requirement areas.

The naming convention of the lifecycle activity categorization is based on the standard ANSI/AAMI SW96 and FDA medical device submission guidance requirements [18–20].

The thematic areas for the technical considerations follow the naming convention of the “Technical Guideline TR-03161” published by the German Federal Office for Information Security (BSI) [21]. Besides the vertical categorization of the cybersecurity lifecycle activities into 11 thematic themes, a categorization in pre-market and post-market activities. Pre-market activities are carried out before a device enters the market, while post-market activities start upon entering the market and go on until the device’s end of life. **Table 1** shows the categorization of the lifecycle activities.

Table 1. Characteristics of included documents. The table provides the complete name of the sources and the type of document.

Pre-Market Activities	Post Market Activities
Develop the system to comply with cybersecurity requirements	Continuously monitor for security incidents and emerging threats.
Conduct threat modeling to identify potential risks and vulnerabilities.	Regularly update and scan SBOMs for vulnerabilities.
Establish controls to mitigate risks and ensure security	Revise threat models and release patches as necessary.
Create a comprehensive cybersecurity management plan	Track and analyze metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of issue detection and resolution.
Implement the system design and generate a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM)	
Assess the SBOM for vulnerabilities and address any identified risks.	
Perform Cybersecurity Testing and Document the Findings	

3.3.1 Cybersecurity Lifecycle Activities

The first category of the defined requirements is “Develop the system to comply with cybersecurity requirements.” ISO IEC TS 27100 mainly discusses the need to develop systems with cybersecurity as a foundational principle. Some standards explicitly recommend adopting security technologies and aligning with international standards like ISO/IEC 27001 to ensure the system is designed to meet all applicable requirements from the early stages, emphasizing secure-by design, e.g., ISO TS 11633-1:2019. Other standards consider this requirement more indirectly by emphasizing creating a robust cybersecurity baseline like ISO TS 82304 or targeting to provide a repeatable and auditable approach to addressing vulnerabilities for manufacturers to achieve compliance like ISO IEEE 11073-40101. Some others emphasize the risk consideration from the early stages and create a framework that ensures that software-related risks are managed throughout the design phase, like IEC 80001-2-2. Some other standards do not consider this requirement, like ISO TR 18307 or ISO IEC TR 22417. Corresponding requirements are covered in 77% (22/30) of the included standards.

The second area of requirements is “Conduct threat modeling to identify potential risks and vulnerabilities.” Standards like ISO/IEC TS 27100:2020(E), and ISO TR 24971:2020, which identify potential threats and vulnerabilities early in the design process, help manufacturers develop effective mitigation strategies. IEC TR 80001-2-9 or ISO 27799 emphasizes identifying threats and vulnerabilities as part of the risk management process, while the standards don't mandate a specific threat modeling methodology. Certain standards, such as ISO/IEEE 11703-401102:2022, incorporate threat modeling methodologies like STRIDE. Corresponding requirements are covered in 60% (17/30) of the included standards.

The third area of requirement is to “Establish controls to mitigate risks and ensure security.” The requirement consideration approach differs from the standard's type and content. IEC 80001-1 calls for "RISK CONTROL" measures to be implemented to reduce the likelihood or severity of harm. This includes design changes, administrative procedures, and user training. This standard defines principles to ensure all implemented controls are documented and traceable. Other standards mention the main specific risk control activities, such as ISO/TR 11636, which recommends specific controls to manage risks and ensure the safety of healthcare information exchange. Corresponding requirements are covered in 67% (19/30) of the included standards.

Specific areas of requirements are not explicitly prescribed in any of the reviewed standards: “Create a comprehensive cybersecurity management plan”, “Implement the system design and generate a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM).” and “Assess the SBOM for vulnerabilities and address any identified risks.” However, some of these standards mention them implicitly. IEC 80001-2-6 requires a risk management plan outlining activities, roles, and responsibilities for all parties operating and maintaining the medical IT network. This can be considered part of a broader cybersecurity management plan, though the document doesn't explicitly use that term. While the TIR does not use the term "Software Bill of Materials," it does state that manufacturers should document the device's assets. This includes information, the device itself, and the components of the device, including software and physical interfaces. This concept aligns with the goals of an SBOM in that it requires a comprehensive list of components that could be a source of vulnerability. The TIR 57 discusses vulnerability analysis. It notes that vulnerabilities can be identified through known vulnerability lists, as well as from the security departments of key customers, and reports of threats experienced by the healthcare system but does not mention assessing SBOMs. “Implement the system design and generate a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM).” is covered in 20% (6/30) of the included standards.

“Perform Cybersecurity Testing and Document the Findings” requirements are mentioned in standards like ISO 81001-1, highlighting the importance of Cybersecurity testing, including penetration testing and vulnerability assessments, for identifying weaknesses and ensuring controls function as intended, while IEC 81001-5-1 defines all types of cybersecurity testing. Corresponding requirements are covered in 57% (16/30) of the included standards.

“Continuously Monitor for Security Incidents and Emerging Threats,” “Regularly update and scan SBOMs for vulnerabilities,” “Revise threat models and release patches as necessary.” and “Track and analyze metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of issue detection and resolution” could be defined as the thematical areas for post-market activities. The “Continuously Monitor for Security Incidents and Emerging Threats” represents the importance of considering incident management and continuous monitoring, mentioned in 18 of the 30 standards (60%). While scanning SBOMs for vulnerabilities is not mentioned in any reviewed standards, “Regularly update and scan SBOMs for vulnerabilities.” is implicitly mentioned by tracking and updating in 9 of the 30 standards (30%). The importance of revising risk management processes, which would include updating threat models and issuing new patches, represents the “Revise threat models and release patches as necessary.” Thematical area. Corresponding requirements are covered in 60% (18/30) of the included standards.

The last defined area of requirements, “Track and analyze metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of issue detection and resolution,” mentioned by several standards, emphasizes the importance of monitoring the effectiveness of risk controls and collecting product security performance information in fielded devices and reporting it back to the manufacturer. Corresponding requirements are covered in 50% (15/30) of the included standards. Table 3 provides an overview of the coverage of the Cybersecurity Lifecycle Activities in the included standards.

Table 3. Coverage of the Cybersecurity Lifecycle Activities in the included standards. The table compares the number of times the defined requirements are met in the standards and shows the percentage of coverage.

	Cybersecurity requirements	Threat modeling	Risk Controls	Cybersecurity management plan	SBOM	Assess the SBOM	Testing	Continuously monitoring	Updates	Revise threat models	Track and analyze
ISO TS 11633-1	*	*	*	*				*		*	*
ISO TS 11633-2	*	*	*	*			*				
ISO TS 82304-2	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO IEEE 11073-40101	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
ISO IEEE 11703-40102	*	*	*	*			*	*		*	
IEC 80001-2-2	*	*	*	*			*	*		*	*
IEC 80001-1	*	*	*	*		*	*	*		*	*
ISO TS 23535	*	*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO IEC TS 27100	*	*	*	*				*		*	*
ISO TR 11636	*	*	*	*							*
ISO TR 18307											
ISO IEC TR 22417											
ISO 14971	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*

IEC TR 80002-1	*											
IEC TR 80002-2												
IEC 62304												
IEC TR 80001-2-9	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO TR 24971	*	*	*	*				*				*
ISO TR 80001-2-6	*		*	*				*				
ISO TR 80001-2-7	*											
ISO 81001-1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO 27799	*	*	*	*			*	*		*		
EN IEC 81001-5-1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO TR 11147												
AAMI TIR57	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
IEEE 11073-10700	*	*	*				*	*		*		
IEEE 11073-10207	*											
IEEE 11073-20701												
IEEE Std 2851							*	*		*	*	*
IEC 80001-2-3	*	*		*			*	*		*	*	*
30	22/30 77%	17/30 60%	19/30 67%	18/30 60%	6/30 20%	9/30 30%	16/30 57%	18/30 63%	9/30 30%	18/30 60%	15/30 50%	

3.3.2 Technical Cybersecurity Considerations

The first category of the defined requirement is “Intended use.” Corresponding requirements are explicitly addressed in standards emphasizing the importance of aligning system objectives with its operational environment and security needs. For instance, ISO 81001-1 provides precise requirements to ensure the intended purpose use for which a product, process, or service is designed according to the specifications, instructions, and information the manufacturer provides. Corresponding requirements are covered in 70% (21/30) of the included standards.

The second category of the defined requirements is “Architecture.” This requirement has been extensively covered, explicitly and implicitly, with several standards focusing on specifying a secure architecture, including requirements for defense-in-depth design, secure design best practices, and architecture reviews mentioned in IEC 81001-5-1. Corresponding requirements are covered in 83% (25/30) of the included standards.

The third category of the defined requirements is “Source code.” While some standards implicitly highlight the necessity of secure coding practices and thorough code reviews, others approach this requirement more indirectly. Corresponding requirements are covered in 37% (11/30) of the included standards.

The fourth requirement category is “Third-party software” standards that address third-party software components or the importance of considering third-party software in risk assessments and responsibility agreements. It requires manufacturers to ensure that third-party suppliers perform applicable security lifecycle activities. This category is considered in 23 standards, equating to 77%.

The fifth category of the defined requirement is “Cryptography.” This requirement ensures data protection through encryption and secure communication protocols. Standards that reference this requirement often align with established cryptographic practices. For instance, IEC TR 80001-2-9 acknowledges cryptography as an essential security control. It provides examples of how cryptographic controls can be used to mitigate specific threats like 'man-in-the-middle' attacks. Cryptography is considered to be 67% (20/30) of the standards.

The sixth category of the defined requirements is “Authentication.” This requirement is a critical aspect of access control to ensure authentication. It highlights the importance of having user registration procedures in ISO 27799 or provides detailed examples of building security arguments around different authentication mechanisms and how to demonstrate confidence in their implementation in IEC TR 80001-2-9. Corresponding requirements are covered in 70% (21/30) of the included standards.

The seventh category of the defined requirements is “Data security.” Standards addressing this requirement highlight the need for robust data security measures to ensure confidentiality and integrity. Data security is treated as a primary concern throughout most of these standards. IEC 62304 is one of them, and it requires establishing a software configuration management process that includes change control procedures. This contributes to maintaining data security by ensuring that changes to software and data are controlled and authorized. Corresponding requirements are covered in 83% (25/30) of the included standards.

The eighth category of the defined requirements is “Network communication.” This requirement appears in 27 of the 30 standards (90%), underlining the importance of secure communication protocols in safeguarding data transmission. ISO TR 80001-2-6, considerations for interface specifications, network compatibility, and potential risks associated with network connectivity are implied.

The ninth category of the defined requirement is “Organizational security.” Organizational-level measures to ensure system security are addressed in 22 of the 30 standards (73%). ISO 81001-1 emphasizes the role of organizational culture and leadership in establishing a culture of safety, effectiveness, and security. It highlights the importance of clear roles and responsibilities, competent personnel, robust policies and procedures, and continuous improvement mechanisms. A strong organizational security posture is essential for effectively managing security risks across the sociotechnical ecosystem.

ISO TR 24971											
ISO TR 80001-2-6	*	*		*			*	*		*	
ISO TR 80001-2-7	*	*		*			*	*	*	*	*
ISO 81001-1	*	*		*		*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO 27799	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
EN IEC 81001-5-1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ISO TR 11147	*	*		*			*	*		*	
IEEE 11073-10700		*			*	*	*	*	*		*
IEEE 11073-10207		*			*	*	*	*			*
IEEE 11073-20701		*			*	*	*	*			*
IEEE Std 2851	*	*	*	*			*	*		*	*
IEC 80001-2-3	*			*	*	*	*	*	*		*
	21/30	25/30	11/30	23/30	20/30	22/30	25/30	27/30	22/30	15/30	24/30
	70%	83%	37%	77%	67%	73%	83%	90%	73%	50%	80%

3.4 Analysis of guidelines and regulations

The scope and regulatory requirements for medical device (MD) manufacturers in the EU are primarily defined by Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council on Medical Devices (EU MDR) [22]. Similarly, requirements for in vitro diagnostic medical devices are outlined in Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and the Council. However, this latter regulation was excluded from the present review. The rules outlined in these regulations are further detailed through guidance documents issued by the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) or by referencing harmonized standards. These harmonized standards are either developed or adapted from existing international standards by European standardization organizations.

In addition to that, several EU-level regulations contain cybersecurity-related requirements potentially relevant for MDs. This includes the NIS Directive or the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). While not being specifically tailored to medical devices, there is an overlap. An overview of the cybersecurity requirements in legally binding EU legislation and guidance is provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Cybersecurity requirements in EU-level legislation and MDCG guidance.

Legislation - Guidance	Cybersecurity related requirements
Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1078 of 14 April 2021 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2021/523 of the European Parliament and of the Council by setting out the investment guidelines for the InvestEU Fund	- Strategic Investments in Cybersecurity - Cybersecurity for Sensitive Facilities - 5G Cybersecurity Toolbox - Cybersecurity Risk Assessment - Defense Sector
Radio Equipment Regulation (EU) 2022/30	- Internet-Connected Radio Equipment - Personal Data and Privacy - Protection from Fraud

	<p>Specific Equipment Categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Childcare Equipment: - Toys - Wearable Radio Equipment
Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 of 17 May 2019 concerning restrictive measures against cyber-attacks threatening the Union or its Member States	<p>Scope of Cyber-attacks Types of Cyber-attacks Threats to Member States Threats to the Union Criteria for "Significant Effect" Restrictive Measures</p>
Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital Technologies and Infrastructure - Cybersecurity Research - Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Robotics - Advanced Computing and Big Data - Space Program - Critical Infrastructure
Single Basic Act.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security Scrutiny for Proposals - 5G Cybersecurity Toolbox - Compliance with Security Requirements: - Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) - Coordination of Security Measures - Security in Funded Actions: - Access to Information - Cybersecurity and Data Protection
NIS 2 Directive.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Cybersecurity Strategies: - Cybersecurity Risk-Management Measures: - Reporting Obligations - Use of European Cybersecurity Certification Schemes - Standardisation: - Supervisory and Enforcement Measures - Cybersecurity Information Sharing - CSIRTs and Cooperation - EU-CyCLONe - Vulnerability Database - Governance
CER Directive.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination with Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS 2 Directive) - Exclusion of NIS 2 Directive Matters - Digital Infrastructure Sector - Financial Sector - Information Sharing - Risk Assessments - Resilience Measures - Incident Notification - National Strategies - Supervision and Enforcement
Cybersecurity Act.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security Objectives - Security by Design - Certification Framework - European Cybersecurity Certificates - EU Statement of Conformity - Assurance Levels - Evaluation Criteria - Technical Specifications and Standards - Voluntary vs. Mandatory Certification - Information Disclosure - National Cybersecurity Certification Authorities
EMA Reinforced Role Regulation,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High Level of Security Controls - Cybersecurity Best Practices - Plan to Prevent, Detect, Mitigate and Respond to Cyber Attacks - Protection of Sensitive Data - Compliance with Data Protection Laws - Protection of IT Infrastructure - Secure Data Exchange - Access Control to the ESMP - Protection of Confidential Information

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparency Measures - Incident Reporting
Machinery Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protection Against Corruption - Software and Data Protection - Cybersecurity Certification - Essential Health and Safety Requirements - Risk Assessment and Reduction - Technical Documentation - Failure of Power Supply or Communication
Chips Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protection of Intellectual Property (IP) Rights and Trade Secrets - Security of Supply Chain and Critical Infrastructure - Monitoring and Risk Mitigation - Access to and Use of Sensitive Information - Data Security and Confidentiality - Cybersecurity Certification - Priority-Rated Orders - Measures Against Third Country Interference
Data Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Protection Measures - Security of Data Transfers - Protection against Unauthorized Use or Disclosure - Trade Secrets Protection - Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities - Security During Switching - International Data Access - Essential Requirements for Interoperability - Smart Contracts - Conformity Assessment - Competent Authorities - Penalties
Artificial Intelligence Act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cybersecurity Requirements for High-Risk AI Systems - Compliance with Horizontal Cybersecurity Requirements: - Risk Assessment - Conformity Assessment: - Derogation for Critical Products - ENISA Cooperation: - Presumption of Conformity - EU Declaration of Conformity - Market Surveillance- - Confidentiality of Information: - Data Protection - AI Regulatory Sandboxes - Real-World Testing - General Product Safety - Transparency
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security of Processing - Pseudonymisation and Encryption - Data Breach Notification - Data Protection by Design and by Default - Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) - Accountability - Controller and Processor Obligations - Cooperation with Supervisory Authorities
European Health Data Space (EHDS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security of Processing: - EHR Systems Certification - Specific Security Requirements - Data Breach Notification - Market Surveillance - Interoperability and Security Standards - Secure Processing Environment - Cross-border Infrastructure - Compliance with other legislation:
Medical Devices Regulation (MDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Safety and Performance Requirements - Software and IT Security - Data Protection and Confidentiality - Risk Management - Post-Market Surveillance - Unique Device Identification (UDI) - Technical Documentation
In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Safety and Performance Requirements - Software and IT Security - Data Protection and Confidentiality - Risk Management - Post-Market Surveillance - Unique Device Identification (UDI) - Technical Documentation

MDCG 2019-16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cybersecurity Risk Assessment Strategies - Continuous Device Security Monitoring - Transparency in Reporting Vulnerabilities - Proactive Approach to Cybersecurity - Collaboration Among Stakeholders - Security by Design Principles - Addressing Vulnerabilities - Post-Market Surveillance - Shared Responsibility
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4. Discussion

4.1 Primary results

The review identified 30 relevant cybersecurity standards for connected medical devices, 17 legally binding documents, and 1 guidance document. The requirements defined by the standards fall into two main categories: "Cybersecurity Lifecycle Activities" and "Cybersecurity Technical Considerations".

Among the Cybersecurity Lifecycle Activities, "Develop the system to comply with cybersecurity requirements" is most frequent, found in 83% of standards. "Regularly Update and Scan SBOMs for Vulnerabilities" is the least frequent, found in 27% of standards. Among the Cybersecurity Technical Considerations "Architecture" is the most frequent, appearing in 87% of standards, while "Source Code" is the least frequent, appearing in 37% of standards.

Several EU-level regulations, such as the NIS Directive and the GDPR, contain cybersecurity requirements overlapping with medical devices. MDCG 2019-16 emphasizes continuous security monitoring, transparency in reporting vulnerabilities, a proactive approach, stakeholder collaboration, and security by design.

4.2 Challenges of current standards and guidelines

The study found that while the identified standards address several aspects of cybersecurity, they sometimes lack detailed methods for integrating these standards into the cybersecurity lifecycle activities. Many standards offer overlapping criteria, creating redundancies, yet also leave gaps where a comprehensive approach is needed. The varying degrees of emphasis on different lifecycle activities, such as the lower frequency of "Regularly Update and Scan SBOMs for Vulnerabilities," suggests that not all critical areas receive the same level of attention across the standards. This inconsistency indicates that while individual standards might contain relevant information, their collective coverage is not complete or uniformly applied.

The existence of multiple standards from different international standardization organizations leads to competing and sometimes deviating requirements. This lack of harmonization makes it challenging for manufacturers to navigate compliance requirements and can lead to confusion and inefficiencies in implementation.

The rapid evolution of cybersecurity presents unique challenges to regulatory frameworks. The dynamic nature of cyber threats means that security measures that are effective today can become obsolete very quickly. This requires regulatory frameworks to be flexible and adaptable, capable of keeping pace with the evolving threat landscape. While including directives like the NIS Directive and GDPR, the existing regulatory landscape does not provide a unified, sector-specific approach to medical device cybersecurity. Regulations such as the Artificial Intelligence Act and Data Act, which also contain cybersecurity aspects, demonstrate multiple legal and regulatory levels to comply with [23,24]. The complexity of this overlapping regulatory space and the speed at which technology evolves constantly challenge regulatory frameworks to remain relevant and effective.

4.3 Future Development

To address the identified challenges, there is a need to develop a harmonized and comprehensive framework that bridges the gaps between technical standards, process-based guidelines, and legislative requirements. Such a framework should streamline compliance processes, reduce redundancies, and ensure clarity in implementing cybersecurity measures across all phases of the medical device lifecycle.

Future efforts should focus on fostering collaboration among regulatory bodies, standardization organizations, manufacturers, and other stakeholders. Enhancing international cooperation could also help align standards globally, reducing barriers to compliance for manufacturers operating in multiple jurisdictions. Additionally, proactive measures such as establishing cybersecurity certification schemes and continuous post-market surveillance mechanisms can further reinforce the resilience of connected medical devices against evolving threats.

By prioritizing these actions, the healthcare industry can create a more secure and trustworthy ecosystem for connected medical devices, ensuring long-term benefits for patients and healthcare providers.

4.4 Limitations

The results of this systematic review could be limited by several factors. First, our review focused exclusively on the EU. This geographic limitation may reduce the applicability of our findings to other regions. Second, this systematic review has an analysis limited to MD-specific guidance documents and standards. This could have led to relevant principles described in standards from other areas not being considered.

4.5 Conclusion

While standards and regulations acknowledge the importance of cybersecurity for connected medical devices, the lack of a harmonized, complete, and adaptable framework creates challenges. Future efforts should focus on developing unified, streamlined guidelines that

minimize redundancies, address inconsistencies, and clarify technical and process-based requirements. Furthermore, collaboration among stakeholders is crucial to ensure a proactive and adaptable approach that safeguards connected medical devices and promotes patient safety in this rapidly evolving technological landscape.

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Author contributions: F.J., O.F., and S.G. developed the design of the study. F.J., K.G., C.R., and F.J. conducted the screening. F.J. conducted the data extraction. F.J. conducted the analysis. F.J. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. O.F., K.G., C.R., and S.G. contributed to the writing, interpretation of the content, and editing of the manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content. All authors had final approval of the completed version and took accountability for all aspects of the work to ensure that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part were appropriately investigated and resolved.

Conflicts of Interest: SG is an advisory group member of the Ernest & Young-coordinated “Study on Regulatory Governance and Innovation in the field of Medical Devices” conducted on behalf of the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety of the European Commission. The authors declare the following competing interests. SG has or has had consulting relationships with Una Health GmbH, Lindus Health Ltd, Flo Ltd, Thymia Ltd, FORUM Institut für Management GmbH, High-Tech Gründerfonds Management GmbH, and Ada Health GmbH, and he holds share options in Ada Health GmbH. OF has a leadership role and holds stock in WhalesDontFly GmbH. FJ declares no competing interests.

Appendix I

Table S1. Description of the included documents.

	Document Title	Type	Description
1	ISO TS 11633-1: 2019 Health informatics — Information security management for remote maintenance of medical devices and medical information systems	Standard	<p>This document focuses on remote maintenance services (RMS) for information systems in healthcare facilities (HCFs) as provided by vendors of medical devices and health information systems.</p> <p>This document specifies the risk assessment necessary to protect remote maintenance activities, taking into consideration the special characteristics of the healthcare field such as patient safety, regulations, and privacy protections.</p> <p>This document provides practical examples of risk analysis to protect both the HCF and RMS provider information assets in a safe and efficient (i.e. economical) manner. These assets are primarily the information system itself and personal health data held in the information system.</p>
2	ISO TS 11633-2:2021 Health informatics — Information security management for remote maintenance of medical devices and medical information systems Part 2: Implementation of an information security management system (ISMS)	Standard	<p>This document gives a guideline for implementation of an ISMS by showing practical examples of risk analysis on remote maintenance services (RMS) for information systems in healthcare facilities (HCFs) as provided by vendors of medical devices or health information systems in order to protect both sides' information assets (primarily the information system itself and personal health data) in a safe and efficient (i.e. economical) manner.</p> <p>This document consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — application of ISMS to RMS; — security management measures for RMS; — an example of the evaluation and effectiveness based on the "controls" defined in the ISMS.
3	ISO TS 82304-2:2021 Health software Part 2: Health and wellness apps — Quality and reliability	Standard	<p>This document provides quality requirements for health apps and defines a health app quality label in order to visualize the quality and reliability of health apps.</p> <p>This document is applicable to health apps, which are a special form of health software. It covers the entire life cycle of health apps.</p> <p>This document is intended for use by app manufacturers as well as app assessment organizations in order to communicate the quality and reliability of a health app. Consumers, patients, carers, health care professionals and their organizations, health authorities, health insurers and the wider public can use the health app quality label and report when recommending or selecting a health app for use, or for adoption in care guidelines, care pathways and care contracts.</p>
4	ISO IEEE 11073-40101:2022 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 40101: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Processes for vulnerability assessment	Standard	<p>Within the context of secure plug-and-play interoperability, cybersecurity is the process and capability of preventing unauthorized access or modification, misuse, denial of use, or the unauthorized use of information that is stored on, accessed from, or transferred to and from a PHD/PoCD. The process part of cybersecurity is risk analysis of use cases specific to a PHD/PoCD.</p> <p>For PHDs/PoCDs, this standard defines an iterative, systematic, scalable, and auditable approach to identification of cybersecurity vulnerabilities and estimation of risk. This iterative vulnerability assessment uses the Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privilege (STRIDE) classification scheme and the embedded Common Vulnerability Scoring System (eCVSS). The assessment includes system context, system decomposition, pre-mitigation scoring, mitigation, and post-mitigation scoring and iterates until</p>

			the remaining vulnerabilities are reduced to an acceptable level of risk.
5	ISO IEEE 11703-40102:2022 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 40102: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Capabilities for mitigation	Standard	<p>Within the context of secure plug-and-play interoperability, cybersecurity is the process and capability of preventing unauthorized access or modification, misuse, denial of use, or the unauthorized use of information that is stored on, accessed from, or transferred to and from a PHD/PoCD. The capability part of cybersecurity is information security controls related to both digital data and the relationships to safety and usability.</p> <p>For PHDs/PoCDs, this standard defines a security baseline of application layer cybersecurity mitigation techniques for certain use cases or for times when certain criteria are met. This standard provides a scalable information security toolbox appropriate for PHD/PoCD interfaces, which fulfills the intersection of requirements and recommendations from National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and the European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA). This standard maps to the NIST cybersecurity framework [B15]; IEC TR 80001-2-2 [B8]; and the Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privilege (STRIDE) classification scheme. The mitigation techniques are based on the extended CIA triad (Clause 4) and are described generally to allow manufacturers to determine the most appropriate algorithms and implementations.</p>
6	IEC 80001-2-2:2012 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-2: Guidance for the communication of medical device security needs, risks and controls	Standard	<p>IEC/TR 80001-2-2:2012(E), which is a technical report, creates a framework for the disclosure of security-related capabilities and risks necessary for managing the risk in connecting medical devices to IT-networks and for the security dialog that surrounds the IEC 80001-1 risk management of IT-network connection. This security report presents an informative set of common, high-level security-related capabilities useful in understanding the user needs, the type of security controls to be considered and the risks that lead to the controls. Intended use and local factors determine which exact capabilities will be useful in the dialog about risk. The capability descriptions in this report are intended to supply health delivery organizations (HDOs), medical device manufacturers (MDMs), and IT vendors with a basis for discussing risk and their respective roles and responsibilities toward its management. This discussion among the risk partners serves as the basis for one or more responsibility agreements as specified in IEC 80001-1.</p>
7	IEC 80001-1:2021 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software	Standard	<p>This document specifies general requirements for ORGANIZATIONS in the application of RISK MANAGEMENT before, during and after the connection of a HEALTH IT SYSTEM within a HEALTH IT INFRASTRUCTURE, by addressing the KEY PROPERTIES of SAFETY, EFFECTIVENESS and SECURITY whilst engaging appropriate stakeholders. IEC 80001-1:2021 cancels and replaces the first edition published in 2010. This edition constitutes a technical revision. This edition includes the following significant technical changes with respect to the previous edition: a) structure changed to better align with ISO 31000; b) establishment of requirements for an ORGANIZATION in the application of RISK MANAGEMENT; c) communication of the value, intention and purpose of RISK MANAGEMENT through principles that support preservation of the KEY PROPERTIES during the implementation and use of connected HEALTH SOFTWARE and/or HEALTH IT SYSTEMS.</p>
8	ISO TS 23535:2022	Standard	This document describes a core set of cloud service

	Health informatics — Requirements for customer-oriented health cloud service agreements		<p>agreements for customer-oriented health cloud services. This document covers a customer-oriented cloud service agreement that can be used in healthcare organizations and public health centers that use health cloud services. This document defines key characteristics in the health cloud service agreement that are indispensable in providing optimal health/healthcare management functionalities. Privacy and security features are considered outside the scope of this document and are covered in ISO/TR 21332.</p> <p>The purpose of this document is to present matters to be considered (e.g., cloud type, components, key characteristics) by stakeholders involved in the implementation of cloud computing in hospitals or healthcare organizations. The potential users of this document are mainly 1) IT managers of hospitals, 2) hospital management, and 3) cloud service providers and cloud partners that provide services to healthcare institutions.</p>
9	ISO IEC TS 27100:2020 Information technology — Cybersecurity — Overview and concepts	Standard	<p>This document provides an overview of cybersecurity. This document:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — describes cybersecurity and relevant concepts, including how it is related to and different from information security; — establishes the context of cybersecurity; — does not cover all terms and definitions applicable to cybersecurity; and — does not limit other standards in defining new cybersecurity-related terms for use. <p>This document is applicable to all types and sizes of organization (e.g. commercial enterprises, government agencies, not-for-profit organizations).</p>
10	ISO TR 11636:2009 Health Informatics — Dynamic on-demand virtual private network for health information infrastructure	Standard	<p>ISO/TR 11636:2009 explains the network requirements in the healthcare field, the network security of an open network for the healthcare field, and the minimum guidelines for security management of health information exchange, including personal data, between external institutions.</p> <p>These requirements will assist in understanding the operation of security and evaluation of security issues in the healthcare field, and the usefulness of a managed VPN, like a dynamic on-demand VPN.</p> <p>ISO/TR 11636:2009 introduces examples of security measures taken in a dynamic on-demand VPN for exchange of medical information; it is not intended to specify the dynamic on-demand VPN itself.</p> <p>These examples provide network solutions to potential risks in such a user environment.</p>
11	ISO TR 18307: 2001 Health informatics — Interoperability and compatibility in messaging and communication standards — Key characteristics	Standard	<p>This Technical Report describes a set of key characteristics to achieve interoperability and compatibility in trusted health information interchange between communicant application systems.</p> <p>The key characteristics describe inter-application interoperability needs of the healthcare community, in particular the subject of care, the healthcare professional/caregiver, the healthcare provider organization, its business units and the integrated delivery network.</p> <p>The key characteristics offer criteria for standards developers and implementers of standards for messaging and communications in the healthcare domain and provide a guide for software developers and vendors, healthcare providers and end users.</p>
12	ISO IEC TR 22417:2017 Information technology — Internet of things (IoT) use cases	Standard	<p>ISO/IEC TR 22417:2017(E) This technical report identifies IoT scenarios and use cases based on real-world applications and requirements. The use cases provide a practical context for considerations on</p>

			interoperability and standards based on user experience. They also clarify where existing standards can be applied and highlight where standardization work is needed.
13	ISO 14971:2019 Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices	Standard	<p>This document specifies terminology, principles and a process for risk management of medical devices, including software as a medical device and in vitro diagnostic medical devices. The process described in this document intends to assist manufacturers of medical devices to identify the hazards associated with the medical device, to estimate and evaluate the associated risks, to control these risks, and to monitor the effectiveness of the controls.</p> <p>The requirements of this document are applicable to all phases of the life cycle of a medical device. The process described in this document applies to risks associated with a medical device, such as risks related to biocompatibility, data and systems security, electricity, moving parts, radiation, and usability.</p> <p>The process described in this document can also be applied to products that are not necessarily medical devices in some jurisdictions and can also be used by others involved in the medical device life cycle.</p> <p>This document does not apply to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — decisions on the use of a medical device in the context of any particular clinical procedure; or — business risk management. <p>This document requires manufacturers to establish objective criteria for risk acceptability but does not specify acceptable risk levels.</p> <p>Risk management can be an integral part of a quality management system. However, this document does not require the manufacturer to have a quality management system in place.</p>
14	IEC TR 80002-1:2009 Medical device software Part 1: Guidance on the application of ISO 14971 to medical device software	Standard	<p>IEC/TR 80002-1:2009(E) provides guidance for the application of the requirements contained in ISO 14971:2007, Medical devices - Application of risk management to medical devices to medical device software with reference to IEC 62304:2006, Medical device software - Software life cycle processes. It does not add to, or otherwise change, the requirements of ISO 14971:2007 or IEC 62304:2006. IEC/TR 80002-1:2009(E) is aimed at risk management practitioners who need to perform risk management when software is included in the medical device/system, and at software engineers who need to understand how to fulfil the requirements for risk management addressed in ISO 14971. ISO 14971, recognized worldwide by regulators, is widely acknowledged as the principal standard to use when performing medical device risk management. IEC 62304:2006, makes a normative reference to ISO 14971 requiring its use. The content of these two standards provides the foundation for this technical report. It should be noted that even though ISO 14971 and this technical report focus on medical devices, this technical report may be used to implement a safety risk management process for all software in the healthcare environment independent of whether it is classified as a medical device. IEC/TR 80002-1:2009 is not intended to be used as the basis of regulatory inspection or certification assessment activities.</p>
15	IEC TR 80002-2: 2009 Medical device software Part 1: Guidance on the application of ISO 14971 to medical device software	Standard	<p>IEC/TR 80002-1:2009(E) provides guidance for the application of the requirements contained in ISO 14971:2007, Medical devices - Application of risk management to medical devices to medical device software with reference to IEC 62304:2006, Medical device software - Software life cycle processes. It does not add to, or otherwise change, the requirements of ISO 14971:2007 or IEC 62304:2006. IEC/TR 80002-1:2009(E) is aimed at risk management practitioners who need to perform risk management when software is</p>

			included in the medical device/system, and at software engineers who need to understand how to fulfil the requirements for risk management addressed in ISO 14971. ISO 14971, recognized worldwide by regulators, is widely acknowledged as the principal standard to use when performing medical device risk management. IEC 62304:2006, makes a normative reference to ISO 14971 requiring its use. The content of these two standards provides the foundation for this technical report. It should be noted that even though ISO 14971 and this technical report focus on medical devices, this technical report may be used to implement a safety risk management process for all software in the healthcare environment independent of whether it is classified as a medical device. IEC/TR 80002-1:2009 is not intended to be used as the basis of regulatory inspection or certification assessment activities.
16	IEC 62304: 2006 Medical device software — Software life cycle processes	Standard	Defines the life cycle requirements for medical device software. The set of processes, activities, and tasks described in this standard establishes a common framework for medical device software life cycle processes.
17	IEC TR 80001-2-9:2017 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-9: Application guidance — Guidance for use of security assurance cases to demonstrate confidence in IEC/TR 80001-2-2 security capabilities	Standard	IEC TR 80001-2-9:2017(E) establishes a security case framework and provides guidance to health care delivery organizations (HDO) and medical device manufacturers (MDM) for identifying, developing, interpreting, updating and maintaining security cases for networked medical devices. Use of this part of 80001 is intended to be one of the possible means to bridge the gap between MDMs and HDOs in providing adequate information to support the HDOs risk management of IT-networks. This document leverages the requirements set out in ISO/IEC 15026-2 for the development of assurance cases. It is not intended that this security case framework will replace a risk management strategy, rather, the intention is to complement risk management and in turn provide a greater level of assurance for a medical device by: - mapping specific risk management steps to each of the IEC TR 80001-2-2 security capabilities, identifying associated threats and vulnerabilities and presenting them in the format of a security case with the inclusion of a re-useable security pattern; - providing guidance for the selection of appropriate security controls to establish security capabilities and presenting them as part of the security case pattern (IEC TR 80001-2-8 provides examples of such security controls); - providing evidence to support the implementation of a security control, hence providing confidence in the establishment of each of the security capabilities. The purpose of developing the security case is to demonstrate confidence in the establishment of IEC TR 80001-2-2 security capabilities. The quality of artifacts gathered and documented during the development of the security case is agreed upon and documented as part of a responsibility agreement between the relevant stakeholders. This document provides guidance for one such methodology, through the use of a specific security pattern, to develop and interpret security cases systematically.
18	ISO TR 24971: 2020 Medical devices — Guidance on the application of ISO 14971	Standard	This document provides guidance on the development, implementation and maintenance of a risk management system for medical devices according to ISO 14971:2019. The risk management process can be part of a quality management system, for example, one that is based on ISO 13485:2016[24], but this is not required by ISO 14971:2019. Some requirements in ISO 13485:2016 (Clause 7 on product realization and 8.2.1 on feedback during monitoring and measurement) are related to risk management and can be fulfilled by applying ISO

			14971:2019.
19	ISO TR 80001-2-6: 2014 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-6: Application guidance — Guidance for responsibility agreements	Standard	ISO/TR 80001-2-6:2014 provides guidance on implementing RESPONSIBILITY AGREEMENTS, which are described in IEC 80001-1 as used to establish the roles and responsibilities among the stakeholders engaged in the incorporation of a MEDICAL DEVICE into an IT-NETWORK in order to support compliance to IEC 80001-1. Stakeholders may include RESPONSIBLE ORGANIZATIONS, IT suppliers, MEDICAL DEVICE manufacturers and others. The goal of the RESPONSIBILITY AGREEMENT is that these roles and responsibilities should cover the complete lifecycle of the resulting MEDICAL IT-NETWORK.
20	ISO TR 80001-2-7: 2015 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices — Application guidance Part 2-7: Guidance for healthcare delivery organizations (HDOs) on how to self-assess their conformance with IEC 80001-1	Standard	ISO/TR 80001-2-7:2015 is to provide guidance to HDOs on self-assessment of their conformance against IEC 80001-1.
21	ISO 81001-1:2021 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security Part 1: Principles and concepts	Standard	<p>This document provides the principles, concepts, terms and definitions for health software and health IT systems, key properties of safety, effectiveness and security, across the full life cycle, from concept to decommissioning, as represented in Figure 1. It also identifies the transition points in the life cycle where transfers of responsibility occur, and the types of multi-lateral communication that are necessary at these transition points. This document also establishes a coherent concepts and terminology for other standards that address specific aspects of the safety, effectiveness, and security (including privacy) of health software and health IT systems.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all parties involved in the health software and health IT systems life cycle including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Organizations, health informatics professionals and clinical leaders designing, developing, integrating, implementing and operating health software and health IT systems – for example health software developers and medical device manufacturers, system integrators, system administrators (including cloud and other IT service providers); b) Healthcare service delivery organizations, healthcare providers and others who use health software and health IT systems in providing health services; c) Governments, health system funders, monitoring agencies, professional organizations and customers seeking confidence in an organization's ability to consistently provide safe, effective and secure health software, health IT systems and services; d) Organizations and interested parties seeking to improve communication in managing safety, effectiveness and security risks through a common understanding of the concepts and terminology used in safety, effectiveness and security management; e) Providers of training, assessment or advice in safety, effectiveness and security risk management for health software and health IT systems; f) Developers of related safety, effectiveness and security standards.
22	ISO 27799:2016 Health informatics — Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002	Standard	<p>ISO 27799:2016 gives guidelines for organizational information security standards and information security management practices including the selection, implementation and management of controls taking into consideration the organization's information security risk environment(s).</p> <p>It defines guidelines to support the interpretation and implementation in health informatics of ISO/IEC 27002</p>

			<p>and is a companion to that International Standard. ISO 27799:2016 provides implementation guidance for the controls described in ISO/IEC 27002 and supplements them where necessary, so that they can be effectively used for managing health information security. By implementing ISO 27799:2016, healthcare organizations and other custodians of health information will be able to ensure a minimum requisite level of security that is appropriate to their organization's circumstances and that will maintain the confidentiality, integrity and availability of personal health information in their care.</p> <p>It applies to health information in all its aspects, whatever form the information takes (words and numbers, sound recordings, drawings, video, and medical images), whatever means are used to store it (printing or writing on paper or storage electronically), and whatever means are used to transmit it (by hand, through fax, over computer networks, or by post), as the information is always be appropriately protected. ISO 27799:2016 and ISO/IEC 27002 taken together define what is required in terms of information security in healthcare, they do not define how these requirements are to be met. That is to say, to the fullest extent possible, ISO 27799:2016 is technology-neutral. Neutrality with respect to implementing technologies is an important feature. Security technology is still undergoing rapid development and the pace of that change is now measured in months rather than years. By contrast, while subject to periodic review, International Standards are expected on the whole to remain valid for years. Just as importantly, technological neutrality leaves vendors and service providers free to suggest new or developing technologies that meet the necessary requirements that ISO 27799:2016 describes. As noted in the introduction, familiarity with ISO/IEC 27002 is indispensable to an understanding of ISO 27799:2016.</p> <p>The following areas of information security are outside the scope of ISO 27799:2016:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) methodologies and statistical tests for effective anonymization of personal health information; b) methodologies for pseudonymization of personal health information (see Bibliography for a brief description of a Technical Specification that deals specifically with this topic); c) network quality of service and methods for measuring availability of networks used for health informatics; d) data quality (as distinct from data integrity).
23	EN IEC 81001-5-1: 2021 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security Part 5-1: Security — Activities in the product life cycle	Standard	<p>This document defines the LIFE CYCLE requirements for development and maintenance of HEALTH SOFTWARE needed to support conformance to IEC 62443-4-1 – taking the specific needs for HEALTH SOFTWARE into account. The set of PROCESSES, ACTIVITIES, and TASKS described in this document establishes a common framework for secure HEALTH SOFTWARE LIFE CYCLE PROCESSES. The purpose is to increase the CYBERSECURITY of HEALTH SOFTWARE by establishing certain ACTIVITIES and TASKS in the HEALTH SOFTWARE LIFE CYCLE PROCESSES and also by increasing the SECURITY of SOFTWARE LIFE CYCLE PROCESSES themselves. It is important to maintain an appropriate balance of the key properties SAFETY, effectiveness and SECURITY as discussed in ISO 81001-1. This document excludes specification of ACCOMPANYING DOCUMENTATION contents.</p>
24	ISO TR 11147:2023 Health informatics — Personalized digital health — Digital therapeutics health software systems	Standard	<p>This document lists characteristics of a category of health software: digital therapeutics (DTx). DTx products generate and deliver medical interventions that are based on clinical evidence, have demonstrable positive therapeutic impacts on patient health, and</p>

			<p>produce real-world outcomes. Product use cases (see Annex B) demonstrate the variety of products represented in this quickly growing industry.</p> <p>This document provides an overview of how DTx relates to other ecosystem constructs, including medical devices, software as a medical device (SaMD), software in a medical device (SiMD), and other digital health technologies (DHT). It also addresses relevant health and medical device software standards that have various degrees of applicability to DTx.</p> <p>The focus of this document is on therapeutic products that are used in the context of a disease, disorder, condition, or injury for human use. It does not address products that are intended for veterinary use or for general wellbeing. Additional exclusions of this document include DTx market access pathways (i.e. prescription, non-prescription pathways), medical device requirements, product risk assessment, clinical evidence requirements, data security, patient privacy considerations, and product authorization pathways.</p>
25	AAMI TIR57:2016 Principles for medical device security - Risk management	Standard	<p>Provides guidance on methods to perform information security risk management for a medical device in the context of the Safety Risk Management process required by ISO 14971. The TIR incorporates the expanded view of risk management from IEC 80001-1 by incorporating the same key properties of Safety, Effectiveness and Data & Systems Security with Annexes that provide process details and illustrative examples.</p>
26	IEEE 11073-10700: 2024 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 10700: Point-of-care medical device communication — Standard for base requirements for participants in a Service-oriented Device Connectivity (SDC) system	Standard	<p>This standard specifies the base set of Participant Key Purposes (PKPs) for the Service-oriented Device Connectivity (SDC) series of standards. PKPs are role-based sets of requirements for products in order to support safe, effective, and secure interoperability in medical IT networks at point-of-care environments such as the intensive care unit (ICU), operating room (OR) or other acute care settings. This standard specifies both product development process and technical requirements.</p>
27	IEEE 11073-10207:2017 IEEE Health informatics--Point-of-care medical device communication Part 10207: Domain Information and Service Model for Service-Oriented Point-of-Care Medical Device Communication	Standard	<p>Within the context of the ISO/IEEE 11073™ family of standards for point-of-care medical device communication, a Participant Model derived from the ISO/IEEE 11073-10201 Domain Information Model is provided in this standard. The Participant Model specifies the structure of medical information objects. This standard also defines an abstract Communication Model to support the exchange of medical information objects. All elements of the Participant Model and Communication Model are specified using XML Schema. Core subjects of the Participant Model comprise modelling of medical device-related data, e.g., measurements and settings, alert systems, contextual information (e.g., patient demographics and location information), remote control, and archival information. Model extensibility is provided inherently through the use of XML Schema. Textual information like patient demographics and location information, remote control, and archival. Model extensibility is provided inherently through the use</p>

			of XML Schema. (Additional files are available for this standard at http://standards.ieee.org/downloads/11073/)
28	IEEE 11073-20701:2020 Health informatics — Device interoperability Part 20701: Point-of-care medical device communication — Service oriented medical device exchange architecture and protocol binding	Standard	The scope of this standard is a service-oriented medical device architecture and communication protocol specification for distributed system of Point-of-Care (PoC) medical devices and medical IT systems that need to exchange data or safely control networked PoC medical devices. It identifies the functional components, their communication relationships as well as the binding of the components and communication relationships to protocol specifications.
29	IEEE Std 2851:2023 IEEE Standard for Functional Safety Data Format for Interoperability within the Dependability Lifecycle	Standard	A dependability lifecycle of products with focus on interoperable activities related to functional safety and its interactions with reliability, security, operational safety and time determinism are defined in this standard. The standard also describes methods, description languages, data models, and database schema that have been identified as necessary or critical, to enable the exchange/interoperability of data across all steps of the lifecycle encompassing activities executed at intellectual property (IP), system-on-chip (SoC), system and item levels, in a way that allows integration in different application domains such as automotive, industrial, medical and avionics safety critical systems.
30	IEC 80001-2-3:2012 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices Part 2-3: Guidance for wireless networks	Standard	IEC/TR 80001-2-3:2012(E), which is a technical report, supports the Healthcare Delivery Organizations (HDO) in the risk management of medical IT-networks that incorporate one or more wireless links. The report, as part of IEC 80001, considers the use of wirelessly networked medical devices on a medical IT-network and offers practical techniques to address the unique risk management requirements of operating wirelessly enabled medical devices in a safe, secure and effective manner. The targeted audience for this technical report is the HDO IT department, biomedical and clinical engineering departments, risk managers, and the people responsible for design and operation of the wireless IT network.
31	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1078 of 14 April 2021 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2021/523 of the European Parliament and of the Council by setting out the investment guidelines for the InvestEU Fund	Regulation	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1078 supplements Regulation (EU) 2021/523 by establishing investment guidelines for the InvestEU Fund. It provides detailed rules on how the Fund should support investments in key sectors like sustainability, innovation, and infrastructure across the European Union, ensuring alignment with EU policies and objectives.
32	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/30 of 29 October 2021 supplementing Directive 2014/53/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the application of the essential requirements referred to in Article 3(3), points (d), (e) and (f), of that Directive (Text with EEA relevance) *referred to as the Radio Equipment Regulation (EU) 2022/30	Regulation	Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/30 supplements Directive 2014/53/EU by providing detailed provisions on the application of essential requirements related to radio equipment. Specifically, it addresses the aspects mentioned in Article 3(3), points (d), (e), and (f) of the Directive, focusing on ensuring safety, health, and electromagnetic compatibility, as well as protecting personal data and privacy. The regulation ensures compliance with EU standards for radio equipment placed on the market within the European Economic Area (EEA).
33	Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 of 17 May 2019 concerning restrictive measures against cyber-attacks threatening the Union or its Member States	Regulation	Council Decision (CFSP) 2019/797 establishes a framework for the European Union to impose restrictive measures (sanctions) against individuals, entities, or bodies involved in cyber-attacks that threaten the EU or its Member States. These measures include asset freezes, travel bans, and prohibitions on making funds available to those responsible for cyber-attacks, including those targeting critical infrastructure, services,

			or institutions. It aims to deter malicious cyber activities and enhance collective cybersecurity resilience.
34	Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU (Text with EEA relevance) *referred to as the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe .	Regulation	Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 establishes the Specific Programme to implement Horizon Europe, the EU's framework programme for research and innovation for the period 2021–2027. This decision outlines the objectives, activities, and implementation measures for the programme, aiming to enhance scientific and technological capacities, address global challenges, and foster innovation in Europe. It repeals Decision 2013/743/EU, which governed the Horizon 2020 programme. The decision also ensures alignment with European Economic Area (EEA) relevance.
35	Council Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 of 19 November 2021 establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe and repealing Regulations (EC) No 219/2007, (EU) No 557/2014, (EU) No 558/2014, (EU) No 559/2014, (EU) No 560/2014, (EU) No 561/2014 and (EU) No 642/2014 *referred to as the Single Basic Act .	Regulation	Council Regulation (EU) 2021/2085 establishes the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe, the EU's research and innovation framework programme for 2021–2027. These Joint Undertakings are public-private partnerships that promote collaboration in key areas like health, energy, digital technology, and climate action. The regulation defines their objectives, funding mechanisms, and governance structures, aiming to drive innovation and address societal challenges. It repeals earlier regulations governing similar partnerships under previous EU programmes.
36	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) (Text with EEA relevance)Text with EEA relevance *referred to as the NIS 2 Directive .	Regulation	Directive (EU) 2022/2555, also known as the NIS 2 Directive, establishes updated rules to achieve a high common level of cybersecurity across the European Union. It replaces the original NIS Directive (Directive (EU) 2016/1148), broadening its scope to include more sectors and entities critical to the economy and society, such as energy, transport, banking, health, and digital infrastructure. The directive introduces stricter security and reporting requirements, improves cooperation and information sharing among Member States, and strengthens the EU's overall resilience to cyber threats. It also amends Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS Regulation) and Directive (EU) 2018/1972 (European Electronic Communications Code), with relevance to the European Economic Area (EEA).
37	Directive (EU) 2022/2557 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on the resilience of critical entities and repealing Council Directive 2008/114/EC (Text with EEA relevance) * referred to as the CER Directive .	Regulation	Directive (EU) 2022/2557, known as the Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive, aims to strengthen the resilience of critical entities that provide essential services in the European Union. It replaces Council Directive 2008/114/EC, expanding its scope to include additional sectors and updated measures to address current risks and challenges. The directive requires Member States to identify critical entities, conduct risk assessments, and adopt measures to enhance the security and continuity of essential services. It applies to sectors such as energy, transport, health, water, and digital infrastructure, ensuring these entities can withstand and recover from disruptions, including physical and cyber-related threats. It also introduces obligations for national strategies and enhanced cooperation among Member States.
38	Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) (Text with EEA relevance) * commonly known as the Cybersecurity Act .	Regulation	Regulation (EU) 2019/881, commonly referred to as the Cybersecurity Act, establishes a strengthened mandate for ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and creates a European cybersecurity certification framework for information and communications technology (ICT) products, services, and processes. Key aspects of the regulation include: Granting ENISA a permanent mandate, enabling it to provide greater support to Member States in improving their cybersecurity capabilities.

			<p>Establishing a European cybersecurity certification framework to ensure the security of ICT products, services, and processes across the EU.</p> <p>Enhancing EU-wide resilience to cyber threats by promoting a high level of cybersecurity through standardized practices.</p> <p>The regulation replaces Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 and applies to the European Economic Area (EEA), ensuring its measures are widely implemented.</p>
39	<p>Regulation (EU) 2022/123 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 January 2022 on a reinforced role for the European Medicines Agency in crisis preparedness and management for medicinal products and medical devices (Text with EEA relevance)</p> <p>* referred to as the EMA Reinforced Role Regulation,</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2022/123, known as the EMA Reinforced Role Regulation, strengthens the European Medicines Agency's (EMA) role in crisis preparedness and management for medicinal products and medical devices. It establishes frameworks to monitor shortages, coordinate responses, and provide scientific advice during public health emergencies. The regulation applies across the EEA.</p>
40	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2023 on machinery and repealing Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 73/361/EEC (Text with EEA relevance)</p> <p>* referred to as the Machinery Regulation</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/1230, known as the Machinery Regulation, updates rules for the safety of machinery and related products in the EU, replacing Directive 2006/42/EC and Directive 73/361/EEC. It aims to ensure high safety standards while facilitating innovation, particularly for new technologies like AI and robotics. The regulation has EEA relevance, ensuring consistent application across the European Economic Area.</p>
41	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe's semiconductor ecosystem and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Chips Act) (Text with EEA relevance)</p> <p>* referred to as the Chips Act</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/1781, known as the Chips Act, establishes a framework to strengthen Europe's semiconductor ecosystem. It aims to boost innovation, increase production capacity, and reduce dependency on external suppliers for semiconductors, ensuring technological leadership and resilience. The regulation amends Regulation (EU) 2021/694 (Digital Europe Programme) and applies across the EEA.</p>
42	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) (Text with EEA relevance)</p> <p>* referred to as the Data Act</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2023/2854, known as the Data Act, establishes harmonized rules to ensure fair access to and use of data across the EU. It aims to promote data sharing between businesses, consumers, and public sector bodies while ensuring data privacy and security. The regulation also amends Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 (Consumer Protection Cooperation) and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Representative Actions Directive). It applies across the European Economic Area (EEA).</p>
43	<p>Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance)</p> <p>* referred to as the Artificial Intelligence Act,</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act) (Text with EEA relevance)</p>
44	<p>the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance))</p> <p>* referred to as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2016/679, widely known as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), sets out comprehensive rules for the protection of personal data in the EU. It ensures the rights of individuals regarding their data, imposes obligations on organizations processing personal data, and standardizes data protection laws across Member States. The regulation also facilitates the free movement of data within the EU while safeguarding privacy. It repeals Directive 95/46/EC and applies to the European Economic Area (EEA).</p>

45	<p>the proposed regulation of EHDS (Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the European Health Data Space) * referred to as the European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	Regulation	<p>The proposed regulation on the European Health Data Space (EHDS) aims to create a common framework for accessing and sharing health data across the EU. It seeks to empower individuals with greater control over their health data, facilitate cross-border healthcare, and promote secondary use of health data for research, innovation, and policymaking.</p> <p>The EHDS regulation is designed to enhance data interoperability, security, and privacy, supporting the EU's goal of a robust digital health ecosystem while maintaining strict data protection standards.</p>
46	<p>the MDR (Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance)) * referred to as the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR)</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2017/745, commonly known as the Medical Devices Regulation (MDR), establishes updated rules for the safety, performance, and market access of medical devices in the EU. It replaces Directives 90/385/EEC (Active Implantable Medical Devices Directive) and 93/42/EEC (Medical Devices Directive) to ensure higher standards for patient safety and device quality.</p> <p>The MDR introduces stricter requirements for clinical evaluation, post-market surveillance, and traceability of devices. It also strengthens oversight by notified bodies and introduces a unique device identification (UDI) system to enhance transparency. The regulation applies across the European Economic Area (EEA).</p>
47	<p>the IVDR (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU (Text with EEA relevance)) * referred to as the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR)</p>	Regulation	<p>Regulation (EU) 2017/746, known as the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (IVDR), establishes updated rules for the safety, performance, and market access of in vitro diagnostic (IVD) medical devices in the EU. It replaces Directive 98/79/EC (IVD Directive) and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU to align with modern standards and improve patient safety.</p> <p>The IVDR introduces stricter requirements for clinical evidence, post-market surveillance, and risk classification of IVDs. It also strengthens oversight by notified bodies and implements a unique device identification (UDI) system to enhance traceability and transparency. The regulation applies to the European Economic Area (EEA).</p>
48	<p>MDCG 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices</p>	Guideline	<p>MDCG 2019-16, Guidance on Cybersecurity for Medical Devices, provides recommendations for integrating cybersecurity into the design, development, and lifecycle management of medical devices. It emphasizes risk management, post-market surveillance, secure updates, and clear documentation to meet requirements under the MDR and IVDR, ensuring safe and secure connected healthcare.</p>